

INTERACTION OF ARYL-SUBSTITUTED THIURETS AND AROMATIC AMINES: SO-CALLED GUANIDINOTHIUREAS AND THEIR ANHYDROACYL DERIVATIVES

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The interaction of aromatic primary amines with aryl-substituted thiurets has been examined. Depending on the conditions of reaction, the product is either an *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-arylthiocarbamide or a 3:5-diarylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole. It has been shown that both, the so-called arylguanidinoarylthiocarbamides and the related anhydro acetyl derivatives, described by Fromm and co-workers, are identical with the corresponding 3:5-diarylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazoles. Mechanism of the changes has been discussed.

Fromm *et al.* reported (*Annalen*, 1906, 348, 174 ; 1907, 356, 178 ; 1908, 361, 321 ; 1912, 394, 258) that when halohydracid salts of aromatic substituted thiurets reacted with aromatic amines, "arylguanidinoarylthiocarbamides"* (I) or (II) were formed:

On acetylation (I) furnished an acetyl derivative (*Annalen*, 1908, 361, 314, 315) which on treatment with alcoholic potash was believed to lose a molecule of water and form an "anhydroacyl arylguanidinoarylthiocarbamide" to which structure (III) has been assigned. Several compounds of the supposed structures (I), (II) and (III) have been prepared (*loc. cit.*).

Suresh has recently shown (*this Journal*, 1960, 37, 30) that the product of the reaction between phenylthiuret and aniline is not the reported "phenylguanidino-phenylthiocarbamide" (I), but is identical with its oxidation product, 3:5-diphenyl-amino-1:2:4-thiodiazole (IV; Ar=Ar'=Ph).

* This nomenclature implies a guanidino group substituted on one of the nitrogens of thiourea. Since only NHAr-C=NH group and not $\text{NHAr(NH}_2\text{)C-NH}$ is actually substituted, the nomenclature is open to objection.

A reinvestigation of the above reactions was therefore undertaken with a view to ascertaining the nature of the products in other cases and also to confirming the structure (III) of anhydroacyl derivatives. Reactions between the following pairs of reactants were examined: (i) *p*-tolylthiuret and *p*-toluidine, (ii) *p*-tolylthiuret and aniline, (iii) *p*-phenetylthiuret and aniline and (iv) phenylthiuret and *p*-phenetidine.

In most cases, when the reaction was carried out under the conditions described by Fromm *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), the major product was found generally to have the melting point reported by these workers. Unlike the thiocarbamides, it was, however, undesulphidable by alkaline lead oxide, and proved identical with a thiodiazole of the type (IV) in which the arylamino group at position-5 represented the arylamino group of the thiuret used. For instance, in the reaction between *p*-tolylthiuret and aniline, the product was 3-phenylamino-5-*p*-tolylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole. Its structure was confirmed in each case by synthesis by the oxidation of the related *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-arylthiocarbamide (Kurzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2345; Suresh, *loc. cit.*). The other product, isolated in much smaller quantities, has not been mentioned by the earlier workers and is really the thiocarbamide represented by structure (I) above. If the thiuret and the amine were allowed to react for a shorter time or at a lower temperature, the compound (I) represented the main product. Its structure was confirmed in each case by its synthesis from the appropriate monoarylguanidine and aryl isothiocyanate,

The product obtained by the action of *p*-phenetidine on *p*-phenetylthiuret has been assigned structure (II) of di-*p*-phenetylguanidinothiocarbamide (*Annalen*, 1912, 394, 262), but this is found to be identical with the *N*-*p*-phenetylformamido *N'*-*p*-phenetylthiocarbamide (I).

The arylformamido-arylthiocarbamides, which is a better name for compound of the type of (I), when boiled for considerable length of time in alcoholic solution, did not undergo any change even when free acid and amines were added; but when finely powdered sulphur was added, oxidation to (IV) took place, as it did with iodine or bromine.

From these results, the following scheme of reactions would appear to represent the sequence of changes in the amine-thiuret interaction:

In the light of these facts, the reported acyl derivatives of "arylguanidinoarylthiocarbamides" should be identical with the acetyl derivatives of the thiodiazoles (IV) as, indeed, has been confirmed. On treatment with alcoholic potash, as

expected, these give back the original thiodiazoles. Identity of the so-called anhydroacetyl-*p*-tolylguanidino-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide with 3:5-di-*p*-tolylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole has been confirmed by analysis comparison of properties and ultraviolet absorption spectra. In other cases, the identity of anhydroacetyl derivatives with the related thiodiazoles has been established by observing undepressed melting points of their mixtures.

EXPERIMENTAL

(1). *Reaction between p-Tolylthiuret and p-Toluidine under Fromm's Conditions: Formation of (IV : Ar=Ar'=p-tolyl).*—*p*-Tolylthiuret (11.25 g.), *p*-toluidine (10.9 g.) and alcohol (50 c.c.) were heated under reflux for 1½ hours on a water-bath. The hot solution was filtered from the precipitated sulphur and allowed to crystallise. Crystals were washed with CS₂ and dried, yield 3.5 g. m.p. 203-205°. When crystallised from alcohol, it melted at 206° (Fromm and Weller, *Annalen*, 1908, 361, 310, record m.p. 170-80°). [Found: C, 64.82; H, 5.49; N, 18.92. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₆N₂S: C, 64.84; H, 5.40; N, 18.91%]. The compound could not be desulphided with lead oxide. Picrate, m.p. 182°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 209° (Fromm and Weller, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 194°).

(2). *Reaction between p-Tolylthiuret and p-Toluidine under Mild Conditions: Formation of p-Tolylformamido-p-tolylthiocarbamide.*—*p*-Tolylthiuret (11.25 g.), *p*-toluidine (10.9 g.) and alcohol (50 c.c.) were heated gently under reflux for 15 to 30 minutes on a water-bath. The hot solution was filtered and allowed to stand when crystals appeared; these were filtered and washed with CS₂, m.p. 156-57°. On recrystallisation from alcohol the m.p. rose to 160°. Picrate, m.p. 174° acetyl derivative, m.p. 192°. (Found: C, 64.01; H, 5.70. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₈N₂S: C, 64.42; H, 6.04%). This was *p*-tolylformamido-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (*vide infra*).

The compound (m.p. 160°), when warmed with lead oxide, blackened it. On oxidation with iodine in alcoholic medium or with bromine in chloroform it afforded a product, m.p. 206°. This was identified (*vide supra*) with the product obtained under (1). Picrate, m.p. 182°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 209°.

(3). *Preparation of N-p-Tolylformamido-N'-p-tolylthiocarbamide from p-Tolylguanidine and p-Tolyl isothiocyanate and its Oxidation to 3:5-Di-p-tolylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole.*—(i). To mono-*p*-tolylguanidine (5 g.), dissolved in alcohol (30 c.c.), *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (4 c.c.) was added and the mixture heated under reflux for 45 minutes on a water-bath. The solution was filtered hot and allowed to cool, when crystals appeared, m.p. 166°. Picrate, m.p. 174°. (Found: C, 64.80; H, 5.79; N, 18.96; S, 10.31. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₈N₄S: C, 64.42; H, 6.04; N, 18.79; S, 10.70%).

Mixed m.p.s of the product and its picrate remained undepressed when mixed respectively with the compound and its picrate, obtained before. Their ultraviolet absorption spectra were also identical (Fig. 2).

FIG. 1

Solvent: EtOH

—○— ... *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-phenyl-thiocarbamide.
 Solid triangle...*N*-*p*-tolylformamido-*N'*-*p*-tolyl- "
 x-x- *N*-*p*-phenetylformamido-*N'*-phenyl- "
 Solid circle...3 : 5-diphenylamino-1 : 2 : 4-thiodiazole.
 —○—3 : 5-di-*p*-tolylamino- "
 - - - - - 3-*p*-phenethylamino-5-phenylamino 1 : 2 : 4-thiodiazole.

(ii). The above *N*-*p*-tolylformamido-*N'*-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (10 c.c.), diluted slightly and acidified with two drops of HCl (conc.). Iodine (1 g.) in aqueous potassium iodide was added gradually till iodine colour persisted, when crystals began to separate. Excess of iodine was removed by adding a pinch of sodium bisulphite. The solution was filtered, m.p. 204° (crude); on recrystallisation from alcohol the m.p. rose to 206°. (Found: C, 65.10; H, 5.53; N, 18.73. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}N_4S$: C, 64.84; H, 5.40; N, 18.91%). Picrate, m.p. 182°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 209°.

This oxidation product was found identical with the product obtained under (1) and the product obtained by iodine or bromine oxidation under (2). The mixed m.p.s with the original products, their acetyl derivatives and picrates showed no depression.

(4). *Oxidation of N-p-Tolylformamido-N'-p-tolylthiocarbamide with Sulphur.*—The alcoholic solution of the above thiocarbamide was heated under reflux with *p*-toluidine and HCl, but it remained unchanged. However, when the thiocarbamide was refluxed in alcohol in presence of finely powdered sulphur, oxidation to thiodiazole occurred. The product separated on crystallisation, m.p. 206°. It was identified with 3:5-di-*p*-tolylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole by undepressed mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

(5). *Preparation of Acetyl Derivative and its Hydrolysis.*—3:5-Di *p*-tolylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole (0.5 g.) was warmed with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) in a water-bath for 15 minutes. The mass was poured in ice water, m.p. 207° (crude); when recrystallised from dilute acetic acid the m.p. rose to 209° (Fromm and Weller, *loc. cit.*, recorded m.p. 194°). The mixed m.p. of the acetyl derivative with the original product was 174-76°. Mixed m.p. with the acetyl derivative obtained under (1) remained undepressed. Thus, the acetyl derivative of the so-called "*p*-tolylguanidino-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide" is really identical with the acetyl derivative of the related thiodiazole.

The acetyl derivative was heated with alcoholic potash (4*N*) under reflux for 2 hours. On dilution and evaporation of the alcohol a product, recrystallisable from alcohol, was obtained, m.p. 206°. (Fromm and Weller's "anhydroacetyl derivative, m.p. 206, *Annalen*, 1908, 361, 315). (Found: C, 64.47; H, 5.52; N, 18.87. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₆N₄S: C, 64.84; H, 5.40; N, 18.91%).

The identity of the above product with the original thiodiazole was confirmed by analysis, by undepressed mixed m.p. and the ultraviolet absorption (Fig. 1).

(6). *Reaction between p-Tolylthiuret and Aniline.*—*p*-Tolylthiuret (11.25 g.), aniline (9.5 c.c.) and alcohol (50 c.c.) were refluxed for 1½ hours on a water-bath. The hot solution was filtered from the precipitated sulphur, when crystals appeared. On washing with CS₂, it afforded crystals, m.p. 182-83°, yield 3 g. On recrystallisation from alcohol, the m.p. rose to 185° (Fromm and Weller, *ibid.*, 1908, 361, 305, recorded m.p. 182°). Picrate, m.p. 181°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 227°.

However, when the reaction was carried out under milder conditions, *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide, m.p. 137°, was obtained as the major product. It was found identical with the product obtained by the condensation of phenylguanidine and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (*vide infra*) by undepressed m.p. of their mixture.

(7). *Preparation of N-Phenylformamido-N'-p-tolylthiocarbamide and its Oxidation to 3-Phenylamino-5-p-tolylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole.*—To monophenylguanidine (5 g.), dissolved in alcohol (30 c.c.), *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (4 c.c.) was added and the mixture heated under reflux for 45 minutes. The hot solution was filtered when crystals separated. The product was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 137-38°. (Found: S, 11.56. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₆N₄S: S, 11.26%).

The above *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (15 c.c.) and an excess of iodine in aqueous potassium iodide was added gradually, when crystals separated. On recrystallisation from alcohol it had m.p. 185°. Mixed m.p. remained undepressed on admixture with the product of the foregoing experiment. Mixed m.p. of their acetyl derivatives also remained undepressed.

(8). *Preparation of Acetyl Derivative and Hydrolysis.*—A mixture of 3-phenylamino-5-*p*-tolylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole (0.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) was warmed on a water-bath for 15 minutes. The mass was poured in ice water and the product recrystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 227° (Fromm and Weller, *loc. cit.*, recorded m.p. 225°). This was found identical with the acetyl derivative described under (6). Thus, the acetyl derivative of the so-called "phenylguanidino-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide" is really identical with the acetyl derivative of the related thiodiazole.

The acetyl derivative was heated with alcoholic potash (4 *N*) under reflux for 2 hours; the reaction mixture was diluted and the alcohol evaporated; the product was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185° (Fromm and Weller, *loc. cit.*, recorded m.p. 185° for the anhydro derivative). The identity of this product with the starting thiodiazole was confirmed by undepressed melting point of their mixture.

Reaction between p-Phenetylthiouret and Aniline.—(i). *p*-Phenetylthiouret (12.75 g.) and aniline (9.5 c.c.) on being heated and treated exactly as under (6), afforded a product in 3.5 g. yield, m.p. 183-84°; recrystallised from alcohol the m.p. rose to 185° (Fromm and Vetter, *Annalen*, 1907, 356, 185, record m.p. 170°). Picrate, m.p. 182°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 139°.

(ii). When heated only for a few minutes, the above reactants furnished *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-*p*-phenetylthiocarbamide (m.p. 124°) which was found identical with the product obtained by the condensation of phenylguanidine and *p*-phenetyl isothiocyanate (*vide infra*).

(10). *Preparation of p-Phenetyl isoThiocyanate.*—Gattermann (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1899, ii, 59, 588) prepared it by the action of thiophosgene and *p*-phenetidine. Now it has been prepared as follows: CS₂ (11 c.c.) and liquor ammonia (23 c.c.) were mixed and cooled in ice. To the cooled mixture *p*-phenetidine (15 c.c.) was added gradually with constant shaking when the ammonium salt of *p*-phenetyldithiocarbamic acid was precipitated. It was filtered out and treated with lead nitrate (75 g.) in water (250 c.c.) and then steam-distilled. A colorless soft solid mass separated out from the distillate. It was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 61°, yield 5.5 g.

The above *p*-phenetyl isothiocyanate was identified by converting it into mono-*p*-phenetylthiourea (m.p. 174°) by treatment with concentrated ammonia. The monophenetylthiourea was also synthesised by heating together ammonium thiocyanate and *p*-phenetidine hydrochloride in an aqueous medium. The product was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 174°. The identity of both the thioureas was established by observing undepressed melting point of their mixture.

(11). *Preparation of N-Phenylformamido-N'-p-phenetylthiocarbamide and its Oxidation to 3-Phenylamino-5-p-phenetylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole.*—Monophenylguanidine (5 g.), dissolved in alcohol (30 c.c.), was added to *p*-phenetyl isothiocyanate (4 g.), and the mixture heated under reflux for 45 minutes. The hot solution was filtered and allowed to crystallise. It was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 124°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: S, 10.14. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₈ON₄S: S, 10.19%). The compound gave no depression in m.p. when mixed with the product obtained under (9, ii).

The above *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-*p*-phenetylthiocarbamide (2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (15 c.c.) and oxidised with iodine as under (3, ii). The product was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185°. The identity of this oxidation product was confirmed with 3-phenylamino-5-*p*-phenetylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole, obtained under (9, i) by undepressed mixed m.p.

(12). *Preparation of Acetyl Derivative and its Hydrolysis.*—3-Phenylamino-5-*p*-phenetylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole (0.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) were heated for a few minutes and then poured in cold water. The crude product (m.p. 137°) was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 139° (Fromm and Vetter, *loc. cit.*, recorded m.p. 172°).

The acetyl derivative was heated with alcoholic potash (4 *N*) under reflux for 2 hours, diluted, alcohol evaporated and the product recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185°. Fromm and Vetter's anhydroacetyl derivative (*loc. cit.*) melted at 187°. Its identity with the original starting thiodiazole was confirmed by undepressed melting point of their mixture. Thus, the acetyl derivative of the so-called "phenylguanidino-*p*-phenetylthiocarbamide" is really identical with the acetyl derivative of the related thiodiazole, and the supposed anhydroacetyl derivative is identical with the thiodiazole itself.

(13). *Reaction between Phenylthiuret and p-Phenetidine.*—(i). Phenylthiuret (10.5 g.), *p*-phenetidine (13.9 c.c.) and alcohol (50 c.c.) were similarly heated as under (6) to furnish 3.5 g. of the product. It was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 181°. Fromm and Vetter, (*loc. cit.*) recorded m.p. 168°. (Found: C, 61.29; H, 5.13. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₈ON₄S: C, 61.54; H, 5.12%). Picrate, m.p. 199°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 185° (Fromm and Vetter, *loc. cit.*, recorded m.p. 183°).

(ii). When phenylthiuret and *p*-phenetidine in the above ratio were heated under reflux for 15 minutes only, the major product was *N-p*-phenetylformamido-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide, m.p. 130°. This was found to be identical with the thiocarbamide obtained in the following experiment by the condensation of *p*-phenetylguanidine and phenyl isothiocyanate. The identity was confirmed by undepressed melting point of their mixture and by ultraviolet absorption spectra (Fig. 1).

(14). *Preparation of N-p-Phenetylformamido-N'-phenylthiocarbamide and its Oxidation to 3-p-Phenetylamino-5-phenylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole.*—The mixture of *p*-phenetylguanidine carbonate (5 g.), dissolved in alcohol (30 c.c.), and phenylisothiocyanate (4 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 45 minutes. The hot solution was filtered and allowed to crystallise. The product was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 130°. This was found identical with the product obtained under (13, ii).

The above *N-p*-phenetylformamido-*N*-phenylthiocarbamide (2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (15 c.c.) and to it excess of iodine in aqueous potassium iodide was added gradually. Crystals separated, m.p. 179-80°; on recrystallisation from alcohol the m.p. rose to 181°. The product was confirmed to be identical with the 3-*p*-phenetyl-amino-5-phenylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole, obtained in the preceding experiment, by undepressed mixed m.p. with their mixture and by ultraviolet absorption spectra (Fig. 1).

(15). *Preparation of Acetyl Derivative and its Hydrolysis.*—3-*p*-Phenetyl-amino-5-phenylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole (0.5 g.) was warmed with acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) for a few minutes. The mass was poured in ice-water. The product was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 185° (Fromm and Vetter, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 183°).

The acetyl derivative was heated with alcoholic potash (4 *N*) under reflux for 2 hours, diluted, alcohol evaporated and the product recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 181° (Fromm and Vetter, *loc. cit.* recorded m.p. 204°). The identity with the original thiodiazole was confirmed by undepressed melting point of their mixture.

(16). *Preparation of Acetyl Derivatives of 3:5-diphenylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole and its Hydrolysis.*—3:5-Diphenylamino-1:2:4-thiodiazole (0.5 g.), prepared by action of aniline on phenylthiuret, was warmed with acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) for a few minutes. The mass was poured in ice water and the product was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 236° (Fromm and Vetter *loc. cit.* recorded m.p. 240°).

The acetyl derivative was heated with alcoholic potash (4 *N*) under reflux for 2 hours. The contents were diluted, alcohol evaporated and the product was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 202°. Fromm and Vetter's anhydroacyl-derivative melted at 200°. The identity with the original thiodiazole was established by undepressed melting point of their mixture. Thus the acetyl derivative of the so-called "phenylguanidinophenylthiocarbamide" is really identical with the acetyl derivative of the related thiodiazole.

(17). *Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of the N-p-Tolylformamido-N'-p-tolyl- and N-p-Phenetylformamido-N'-phenylthiocarbamide and their Oxidation Products, the Thiodiazoles.*—The substance (0.0004 g.) was dissolved in 10 c.c. of absolute alcohol and ultraviolet absorption was recorded on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. The curves are shown on the accompanying graph. The curves for formamido-thioureas are similar to that obtained for *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide and those of their oxidation products are similar to that of 3:5-diphenyl-amino-1:2:4-thiodiazole.

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